

TRAIN4EU

Transforming ReseArch & INnovation

Agendas and support in 4EU+

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**D 4.3 Report on transformative change potential and piloting,
Citizens – Academia – Business**

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Sorbonne University

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DELIVERABLE OVERVIEW

Deliverable title:	Transformative change potential and piloting of the Citizen-Academia-Business Link
Work package:	WP4 Linking Citizen-Academia-Business [M 1-35] / Univ. of Sorbonne
Description of the deliverable:	The aim of this deliverable is to describe TRAIN4EU WP4 task 3. The partners describe actions realized on relevant and common activities in linking Citizen, Academia and Business across 4EU+ Alliance universities.
Prepared by:	SU : Lucas Ravaux, Lise Tourneux Ravel, Yolima Fauchet, Yoann Haettich, and partners within universities UM: Alessandro Satta, CU: Ivana Sykorova, Ivona Harvey, HU: Raoul Haschke, UCPH: Jacob Juul Gade, UW: Kazik Anhalt.
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INTRODUCTION

At the end of the previous task 4.2 dedicated to the analysis of chosen case studies (see D4.2 / M16), WP4 – TRAIN4EU members proposed to continue considering the following pilot activity: 4EU+ Knowledge and Technology Transfer Platform.

The first step was to identify specific activities that needed to be carried out between the partners and were feasible in terms of human resources while addressing the partners' specific problems and needs.

The following subjects/activities of interest were consequently identified in the task 4.3:

1. Technology transfer for SSH; “Non-commercial knowledge transfer” - **Led by CU**
Participants: CU, SU, UH, UM
2. Entrepreneurship support and training for researchers and students:
Develop and adapt training for young (post-doc) and senior researchers /
Raising awareness researchers and helping in the creation of start-ups – **Led by SU.**
Participants: SU, UW (TTO), UCPH, UH, UM
3. Improving relationships between researchers and companies. **Led by UCPH**
Participants: UCPH, UW

1. Technology transfer for SSH; “Non-commercial knowledge transfer” – Charles University, Sorbonne University, University of Heidelberg

Pilot activity:

organization or planning/design of workshops about non-commercial transfer, with an emphasis on transfer from Social Sciences and Humanities, in each of the participating universities to get feedback and share solutions and good practices.

Team:

Ivana Sykorova, Ivona Harvey (CUNI), Barbara Van Doosselaere (SU), Raoul Haschke (UHEI)

Aim

Support of the social sciences and humanities and non-for-profit transfer from both, STEM and SSH, have been among the topics of interest raised by project partners since the beginning of TRAIN4EU WP4 activity.

Rationale:

The importance of supporting SSH research and non-profit transfer has been a recurring theme among project partners since the inception of TRAIN4EU WP4. Despite the strong presence of SSH fields in our universities, there is a lack of dedicated support for SSH transfer, with technology transfer continuing to dominate. To address this gap, CUNI, UHEI, and SU have partnered to develop these workshops.

Implementation:

To effectively pilot our workshop concept, we propose conducting in-person workshops at each participating institution. This individualized approach will allow for tailored content and discussions specific to each university's context.

Actions realized:

Summary of Activities

- Online team calls – February, June, and November
- 7 workshops realized (CUNI 3, UHEI 3, SU 1)
- 58 participants (CUNI 25, UHEI 18, SU 15)
- 3 workshops planned for October - December 2023 period (CUNI 2, UHEI 1), expected 50 participants (CUNI 35, UHEI 15)
- All in person however different formats
 - CUNI 2-3 hours interactive workshop as a part of a regular educational course or as a tailor-made workshop at the faculty/for the research team, PhD. group etc.
 - SU one-day workshop, design thinking methodology
 - UHEI 2 hours interactive workshop followed up by a networking events
- In Czech (CUNI), French (SU), German/English (UHEI)
- Target group: mixed - early-stage researchers (doctoral students, postdocs, young researchers), Master students, Research Engineers

Workshops format

Charles University Workshop - Your research topic: “a practical use you may not have thought of”

1. AIMS and SCOPE

- To motivate and inspire, to offer a different perspective than pure science
- To show how to think about studies and research in a way that helps find the potential for real-world application and why thinking about impact is useful also for grant calls
- To stress the importance of making a positive impact on society and creating value from the research/PhD/Master thesis
- To share examples of SSH and non-for-profit transfer and practical use of research results to show what is possible to do with the expertise you gained

2. MAIN STAKEHOLDERS

Open to the whole Charles University auditorium as access to the workshop was not limited. We aim primarily for PhD. and Master students, and young researchers. The workshop has been relevant to all disciplines taught at the university, not restricted only to SSH.

3. FORMAT

- **Two pathways**
 1. Workshop as a part of the regular educational course within voluntary courses for students, credits possible (three of five blocks, one block more theoretical, one practical where we discuss with the participants potential use of their research results or their other ideas and prepare them for presentations, third/final one is devoted to presentation/trial pitch of their topic with feedback of our transfer team members). One block is 2-3 hours long, ideally with 15-20 participants. We also invite guests, academics or students of the university to present their stories.
 2. Independent/tailor-made workshop with a length of around two hours, similar content like above mentioned and moreover fully adaptable for the needs of the participants
- **Content consists of two parts**
 1. General – for inspiration/motivation
 - why it is important to look at research in a broader context?
 - motivation factors
 - what are the latest trends/approaches in the Czech Republic/Europe and the UK universities and society?
 - terms used - Technology Transfer / Knowledge Transfer / Impact / Valorisation / Knowledge Exchange /SSH/ SHAPE
 - Current importance of social impact in science, what emphasis is placed on it in national and European grant and project funding sources?
 - what routes to take with research results (commercial and non-commercial)?
 - where to look for funding?
 - links to the SDGs (framework for proving impact)
 - case studies – many examples with links
 2. Interactive discussion of research topics raised by participants, divided into groups with one mentor for each – WHAT, WHY, HOW - What is your research about? What might be an applicable outcome? Who would use the output? Who would be willing to pay the minimum cost? What are the barriers? Would you need any help to develop the idea?

University of Heidelberg Workshop – Bridging the gap

1. AIMS and SCOPE

- To inspire students that there are different career paths
- To broaden students' knowledge about entrepreneurship in general
- To show students that there are different ways of bringing research results into society
- To reflect how students own research can be made accessible for society
- To bring the transfer activities and support mechanisms at UHEI to their attention

2. MAIN STAKEHOLDERS

- Open to every PhD student and scientific employee at UHEI
- Open to all disciplines, interdisciplinary teams are strongly encouraged
- The transfer agency as the organizing team

3. FORMAT

- The Workshop was divided into two parts
 1. The organisers give an overview on entrepreneurship and the different transfer paths (in total 13 different ways, from startup to political advice services)
 2. The participants team up and get the task to develop a transfer strategy for their own research project. The organisers support the process with Design Thinking methods. After finding the right transfer path additional question, like funding or stakeholders are discussed.

The aim is to motivate the participants to move with their idea into the individual coaching sessions of hei_INNOVATION to pursue their newly developed idea.

Sorbonne University Workshop - Innovation and Creativity "capsules"

1. AIMS and SCOPE

- Sorbonne University (SU) hosted a one-day workshop centered on the enrichment of design and the advancement of knowledge within the social sciences and humanities (SSH). Originally planned for an earlier date, this event took place the 10th of November at the SU FabLab and was collaboratively organized by SU's Research Directorate and an innovative partnering agency.
- The workshop's primary objective was to collaboratively explore diverse avenues for enriching SSH research beyond the conventional scopes of patenting, licensing, and entrepreneurial pursuits.
- The core ambition was to foster a wide array of perspectives by reframing knowledge exchange through the prism of social impact. This interactive endeavor aimed to serve society's interests, moving beyond the boundaries of traditional technology-centered innovation paradigms.
- Participants were encouraged to contemplate and share their visions for crafting shared tools that stimulate unconventional thinking and broaden the accessibility of scientific knowledge

2. TARGET AUDIENCE

- This program is designed for project holders (doctoral students, researchers, engineers) seeking to explore deeper into the intersections between the academic, socioeconomic, and sociocultural realms without compromising scientific rigor.

- Participation is open to the entire Sorbonne University community, including members from partner institutions such as CNRS and the National Museum of Natural History.

3. FORMAT

- The workshop employs design thinking methodologies, equipping participants with a set of creative tools to generate novel solutions, identify their optimal implementation strategies, and deploy them effectively.
- The format comprises a full ideation day structured into four phases: Context Analysis, Gap Analysis and Diagnosis, Design, and Experimentation.
- Participation is capped at approximately 15 individuals.
- An "open and welcoming" approach encourages participants to join with their teams and project materials.
- Key Takeaways: Participants will gain a personalized toolkit for crafting their own roadmap for knowledge exchange and transfer, venturing beyond the confines of conventional technology-driven innovation processes.

Feedback from the participants:

The workshop was enriching, pushing the participants out of their comfort zone and highlighting the importance of understanding user needs. It emphasized the importance of putting oneself in the user's shoes and aligning actions with both professional identity and humanistic goals.

The format of the workshop was deemed highly suitable, with effective exposure, feedback reception, and varied content. The individual guidance received was appreciated for its adaptability and innovative solutions. No particular suggestions were made for improvement, except a minor remark on the rhythmic aspect, suggesting it could aid in managing the overall tempo.

Lessons learnt and future prospects:

- We have successfully developed and tested diverse formats of workshops to address this topic within our universities;
- At CUNI and UHEI the workshops organized have become a regular feature and CUNI has been intensifying the tailored offer for faculty researchers and their PhD students. SU is also likely to offer the same format next year.
- Substantive and functional in-person participation on workshops, not online
- We have established close contact among the partner institutions with strong potential for future collaboration e.g., consider a joint project to further develop support for SSH in particular across the 4EU and connect with the remaining (and new) consortium partners. In line with EU Guiding principles for knowledge valorization.

Before the end of the project, in December we will have a meeting to share the output of the Sorbonne format of the workshop as well as discuss how to profit and proceed further with our pilot activity.

2. Entrepreneurship support and training for researchers and students - SORBONNE UNIVERSITE

In this activity, two topics have been identified:

- A. Entrepreneurship support and training for researchers
- B. Entrepreneurship training for students

A. Entrepreneurship support and training for researchers

Pilot activity:

This activity has been created to detect needs in universities about entrepreneurship for researchers and to determine what type of solutions are implemented. The idea was also to analyse if it would be possible to create synergies by sharing courses or workshops between different programs.

Team:

Yolima Fauchet, Lucas Ravaux, Lise Tourneux-Ravel (SU) Alessandro Satta (UM)

Aim:

The aim of this group was to share different experiences in universities regarding training and entrepreneurship support for researchers and students and find synergies.

Sorbonne University (SU) invited WP4 participants to identify and address challenges related to entrepreneurship among researchers. The following key issues emerged:

- **Limited Awareness of Entrepreneurship Pathways:** Many researchers express interest in entrepreneurship but lack guidance on how to proceed and where to seek support. Faced with the desire to establish a startup, they struggle to navigate the complex university ecosystem and identify the most suitable support resources.
- **Focus on Research over Business Acumen:** Researchers often prioritize their research endeavors, leaving limited time and energy to explore business models, market needs, and go-to-market strategies. They recognize the need for assistance in these areas to effectively translate their research into viable business ventures.
- **Lack of Specialized Support for Researchers:** While numerous entrepreneurship programs cater to students, researchers face unique challenges due to the complexities of intellectual property (IP) and the potential for longer time-to-market cycles. Moreover, innovative research often disrupts existing markets or creates entirely new ones, requiring specialized support tailored to these unique circumstances.
- **Ineffective Technology Transfer:** Researchers often possess deep expertise in their technology but lack a clear market approach. They require guidance on translating their technological advancements into commercially viable products or services.
- **Scarcity of Spinoff Creation Programs:** The absence of specific programs dedicated to assisting researchers in establishing spinoffs hinders their ability to translate their research into marketable ventures.
- **IP Awareness Gap:** Researchers often lack adequate understanding of IP protection and may hesitate to engage with technology transfer offices (TTOs) due to concerns about IP management and ownership.
- **Limited Support for Early-Stage Researchers:** While numerous programs exist to support established companies through incubation and acceleration, researchers often lack access to comprehensive support during the early stages of their entrepreneurial journey, prior to formal company creation.

These challenges highlight the need for tailored support programs specifically designed to address the unique needs of researchers venturing into the realm of entrepreneurship. By providing comprehensive guidance and assistance, universities can foster a culture of innovation and entrepreneurship among their researchers, enabling them to successfully translate their groundbreaking research into impactful business ventures.

Entrepreneur-researchers needs detected in universities:

We defined different needs existing at SU and UM:

Pre-Creation Needs: Nurturing Entrepreneurial Insights

- Acculturate researchers into the world of business, its requirements, and its ecosystem
- Provide comprehensive fundraising guidance to support R&D and testing phases
- Offer concise entrepreneurial training programs specifically designed for researchers
- Support researchers in structuring their entrepreneurial projects
- Assist researchers in forming effective entrepreneurial teams with complementary skills

Post-Creation Needs: Sustaining Entrepreneurial Success

- Provide continuous funding support for researchers post-startup creation
- Offer mentorship and guidance from experienced entrepreneurs and business professionals
- Create an environment that encourages researchers to pursue entrepreneurial aspirations

By addressing these needs, universities can empower university researchers as entrepreneurial innovators, fostering a culture of innovation and entrepreneurship that will drive economic growth, societal progress, and the advancement of knowledge.

Summary of Synergistic Ideas for Fostering Entrepreneurial Collaboration

Sorbonne University (SU) has identified several potential collaborative activities that could be implemented among 4EU+ universities to enhance entrepreneurial support and opportunities for the wider community. These initiatives aim to foster knowledge sharing, expand horizons, and cultivate a thriving entrepreneurial ecosystem.

Idea 1: Entrepreneurship Program Exchange

- **Sharing Program Content:** Each university will present the content of their existing entrepreneurship programs, providing insights into their unique approaches and strengths.
- **Feedback and Evaluation:** Participants will share feedback on the various programs, identifying areas for improvement and potential synergies.
- **Cross-Institutional Collaboration:** Themes, seminars, or modules deemed beneficial to all universities will be identified for potential sharing, ensuring accessibility in both English and the local language with translation services.
- **Synergy Discussions:** Open discussions will explore opportunities for collaboration and resource sharing, paving the way for joint ventures and mutually beneficial partnerships.

Idea 2: Addressing Uncovered Topics of Common Interest

- **European Funding Landscape:** Experts will provide comprehensive guidance on navigating European funding opportunities, including the European Innovation Council (EIC) Pathfinder and Accelerator programs.

- **EIT Services:** Representatives from the European Institute of Innovation and Technology (EIT) will showcase their services, offering insights into their operations, success stories, and potential benefits for entrepreneurs.
- **European Standards and Regulations:** Workshops and seminars will address the intricacies of European standards and regulations, particularly those pertaining to medical devices and clinical trials, empowering entrepreneurs to navigate the regulatory landscape effectively.
- **Market Expansion Strategies:** Experienced professionals will share strategies for expanding entrepreneurial ventures beyond Europe, providing valuable insights into global markets and opportunities.
- **International Fundraising:** Sessions will equip entrepreneurs with the knowledge and tools to secure international funding, expanding their financial resources and global reach.
- **Business Plan and Business Model Development:** Dedicated workshops will guide participants in crafting compelling business plans and business models, laying the foundation for sustainable entrepreneurial success.

Idea 3: Nurturing an Entrepreneurial Culture within the Research Community

- **Entrepreneurship Awareness Webinars:** A series of short webinars will be organized to raise awareness of entrepreneurship among researchers, showcasing the benefits and potential of translating research into viable business ventures.
- **Entrepreneurial Success Stories:** Inspirational testimonials from successful entrepreneurs will be shared to motivate and inspire researchers to embrace entrepreneurial aspirations.

By implementing these synergistic initiatives, 4EU+ universities can foster a collaborative environment that empowers entrepreneurs, promotes knowledge exchange, and expands the entrepreneurial horizons of the research community. This collective effort will contribute to the growth of a vibrant entrepreneurial ecosystem, driving innovation and societal advancement.

Entrepreneurial programs in universities: Milan and Sorbonne Universities

Finally, the members of this activity (UM and SU) shared feedbacks of programs in universities. These programs are described below:

a. University of Milan :

Program 1: Student innovation lab

The goal of Student Innovation lab is the creation of an ecosystem of initiatives and services aimed at offering to students:

- a multidisciplinary context for learning methodologies, skills, tools to manage innovation projects;
- paths and activities for the generation, development and acceleration of innovative ideas and projects.

Two different actions are realized in two sessions per year:

- 1) Training and empowerment: aimed to transfer knowledge and useful tools for the development of innovative projects with transversal managerial skills, entrepreneurship and thematic modules (social innovation, sustainability, health, etc.) and to support the various projects of the participants by offering them mentoring, workshops with companies and other interlocutors, business launch simulations, support for crowdfunding

(specific training, campaign design, etc.). The participants will work on the further development of their own ideas.

- 2) Acceleration: tools and services to support the implementation of innovative projects.

Program 2: Seed4Innovation training for students

There are 3 training phases during the program in 1 session per year:

- 1) a general training phase on the topics of entrepreneurship, intellectual property protection, business development and communication.
- 2) a second phase where selected participants will have the opportunity to develop their projects through a specific mentoring process, meeting experts of different sectors.
- 3) a third phase where the selected projects access an accelerator program coordinated by mentors from the promoting institutions, aimed at verifying industrial or commercial feasibility.

b. Sorbonne University

Sorbonne University has developed an entrepreneurial program specifically designed for researchers, PhD candidates, and postdoctoral fellows. This program, named "myStartup Program," was launched in September 2022 and has already supported 20 projects, with an average of 7 projects per 6-month session. The program's objective is to promote the valorization of research results through spin-off creation.

The myStartup Program caters to a wide range of project maturity levels, accepting projects from Technology Readiness Level (TRL) 3 to TRL 9. This flexibility allows participants to join the program at various stages of their entrepreneurial journey, from initial ideation to pre-commercialization.

Throughout the 6-month program, participants enroll in comprehensive courses designed to accelerate their project development. They receive guidance on conducting in-depth market analyses, refining their business models, and preparing for spin-off creation. The program's flexible structure enables participants to engage in the learning process even if they are not physically present at the university.

myStartup Program proposes:

- 1) Collective support : 15 workshops on the different aspects of startup creation :
 - Ecosystem and the major stages in creating a startup
 - Identify your market, position yourself and know how to sell
 - Learn how to present your project
 - How to finance your startup?
 - Intellectual property strategy
 - Thinking about environmental and social impacts
 - Accounting documents and business plan
 - Financial strategy
 - Build a development plan for your technology
 - Understand the role of design in the creation of a startup
 - What skills will make your project a success?
 - Partnering and building your team
 - Sell your product/service
 - Preparing for the final pitch
 - Present your project to investors and future partners

- 2) 360) Project Diagnosis: An in-depth brainstorming session that delves into all aspects of the project, including technical stages, intellectual property, market potential, environmental and social impact, team expertise and roles, and financing strategies. This analysis provides valuable insights and suggestions for advancement across various areas, along with introductions to relevant individuals within the ecosystem who can further support the project's progress.
- 3) Personalized Mentorship: Participants engage in one-on-one sessions with experienced mentors and experts from the innovation and entrepreneurship ecosystem. These mentors provide constructive feedback, challenge assumptions, and guide project leaders in structuring their ventures effectively, ensuring their alignment with industry standards and best practices.

The myStartup Program has received significant recognition and support from the research community. Participants have expressed their satisfaction with the program, highlighting the value of academic guidance and the opportunity to connect with fellow project leaders who share similar challenges and aspirations. The program has successfully expanded its reach beyond Sorbonne Université, welcoming researchers from other local universities within the Sorbonne University Alliance, fostering a broader network of collaboration and innovation.

This positive reception is a testament to the program's effectiveness in addressing the unique needs of researchers venturing into the entrepreneurial realm.

Lessons learnt and future prospects:

Our discussions revealed that organizing joint entrepreneurial events in the short term presents several challenges:

- **Local Focus:** Entrepreneurial fundamentals are typically covered in local programs and delivered in the local language, making it difficult to create common events that cater to a broad audience across multiple universities.
- **Narrow Common Topics:** Identifying common topics of interest beyond the basics proves challenging due to the diverse sectors represented by the projects and the fluctuating number of projects interested in specific topics at any given time.
- **Resource Constraints:** Organizing events, workshops, and conferences for different audiences across multiple universities requires significant time and resources, which may be limited given the relatively small number of entrepreneurial projects involved.
- **Varied Interest Levels:** The level of interest in entrepreneurship within universities varies significantly, influenced by national or regional initiatives. Differences in funding and legal frameworks incentivize entrepreneurs to seek support locally at the initial stages of their ventures.
- **Existing European Support Mechanisms:** Various schemes already exist in major European cities to assist entrepreneurs in accessing European funding and support, such as EIT's Knowledge and Innovation Communities (KICs).

Given these challenges, it may be more effective to focus on strengthening existing local entrepreneurial support initiatives and fostering collaboration among universities in areas where common interests and opportunities arise

B. Entrepreneurship training for students

Pilot activity:

This activity has been started by Sorbonne University and the aim have been to extend an entrepreneurial diploma for students in different universities of the Alliance 4EU+.

Team:

Valérie Patrin Leclerc and Philippe Lebaron (SU), Agnieszka Postuła and Dorota Marszałek (WU), Natalia Pia Ringoli, Clodia Vurro and Edda Cecilia Orlandi (UM), Amelie Vermeer, Raoul Haschke (UH).

Aim:

To develop the program of the diploma “Entrepreneurial and intrapreneurial project management” in 4EU+ universities

“Entrepreneurial and intrapreneurial project management” University Diploma description

On the sidelines of this activity, we would like to present a project close to the theme of entrepreneurship initiated and coordinated by Sorbonne Université with the universities of Heidelberg, Warsaw and Milano.

In autumn 2020, CELSA, the school of communication from Sorbonne University has launched the “Entrepreneurial and intrapreneurial project management” University Diploma (UD) in the context of the Covid 19 health crisis.

The aim was to provide recently graduated students with additional training in the fundamental elements in entrepreneurship (as the crisis led to a decrease in recruitment).

In autumn 2022, based on the success of the first two years and after collaborative work between interested universities, the Sorbonne Université UD was open to 4EU+ Master’s degree students of Heidelberg, Milano and Warsaw.

Aim of the diploma:

This diploma enables graduates to work for a big company in intrapreneurship, a start-up or to develop associations or organizations committed to social, economic or ecological transformation.

It is designed for recently graduated students who want to use their expertise and energy for an innovative project, who want to learn how to work in a team and be introduced to a multidisciplinary approach. It is based on experiential learning, which emphasizes learning through action. In the context of this diploma, the company and partner institutions present a project or a challenge that is extremely innovative. The students are divided into project teams to work together solving the issue.

The “Entrepreneurial and intrapreneurial project management” University Diploma has two main components:

- The first is 80 hours of classes in the fundamental elements in entrepreneurship: identify opportunities and co-building using design thinking to propose innovative solutions, settle on an economic model, look for financing, take a creative approach, launch a business activity using bootstrapping, make a convincing case to stakeholders. Most of the class will be held online and in English.
- The second component is a real project management case on innovation about a subject raised by one of the university partner organisations, supported by a pedagogical

framework and to learn intrapreneurial project management fundamentals. The multidisciplinary teams work for six months in order to design, test and present an innovative solution to the given challenge. This practical exercise allows students to develop skills to lead innovative projects, manage teams and multidisciplinary approaches.

- The program is for one academic year.

Results:

The university diploma was successfully developed in various 4EU+ universities in 2022. To date, 55 students have completed the program (14 UH, 10 UW, 7 UM, 2 SU as part of the European curriculum and 22 SU as part of the French curriculum).

3. Improving relationships between researchers and companies – University of Copenhagen

Improving relationships between researchers and companies: Identifying issues, needs and possible solutions.

Reasoning:

Universities constantly work with developing and expand our collaboration with companies and the surrounding society. The WP4 group of TRAIN4EU have identified three key themes related improving the relationship between researchers and companies. The three identified are:

1. Keeping and developing industrial involvement in research
2. Improving relationships with SME's
3. How to utilize the strength of our networks/clusters and putting it to more fruitful use

Out of discussions with the WP4-group but also with WP4 team it became apparent that we did not have an overview of issues within the three themes and neither of the related needs. It was therefore decided to focus the activity on identifying issues, needs and possible solutions.

Purpose:

The purpose of the activity was to create an overview of issues, needs and possibilities that could be used by individual universities or among 4EU+ universities to create actions that could deal with the identified issues.

Activities:

The group have carried out analyses to identify key issues and needs to be addressed if we collectively want to improve the relationships between researchers and companies.

The work on issues and needs also led to the suggestion of some possible solutions as well as the understanding that many of the needs could be translated into being solutions.

The result is a collection of needs and issues as well as a few suggestions for possible solution within the three themes:

1. Keeping and developing industrial involvement in research
2. Improving relationships with SME's
3. How to utilize the strength of our networks/clusters and putting it to more fruitful use

Theme	Issues	Needs	Solutions
1.	11	3	5
2.	8	8	1
3.	3	8	0

The key take-aways from the desk research:

- There are a lot of issues to tackle.
- Most of the needs could be translated into solutions.

Faculty of Science – UCPH have used the findings to start work on:

- How to merit researchers working with industry.
- Guidelines and education for researchers on possible formats for working with industry.

- Change of Scientific Environment (COSE) for PhD's out into companies (instead of having the Change of Scientific Environment at another university).
- A communication plan towards industry on collaboration formats with university.
- Discussions with national SME cluster organizations on how they can assist the universities in establishing relations and collaborations with SME's.

A specific idea from the group.

It has become clear that a valuable aspect of WP4 is having a forum of colleagues across universities that have different experiences in implementing solutions and working with relationships. We therefore suggest finding a way of keeping in touch and finding a format where it is possible to request feedback on ideas or asking if other universities have possible solutions after the project TRAIN4EU.

The idea:

When starting development or launch of new strategies, ideas or activities within collaboration with citizen-business-academia it should be possible to seek know-how and experience among colleagues within 4EU+ that might already have experience with similar activities. The colleagues could then suggest possible solutions or give feedback on a specific strategy, idea or activity.

Format:

It should be kept simple.

- Starting with an email stating what the issue is. "Subject: WP4 Advice need: [Topic]" and then a short description in the email.
- All have the possibility of responding if they have any experience or would like to comment based on interest in the topic in general.
- Then the person posing the request can call the responders for an online meeting.
- At the meeting they should present the issue and others can give feedback.

Outcome:

- Network and access to colleagues within the area
- Faster implementation of ideas, strategies, and activities within Alliance4EU+.
- Avoiding possible pitfalls that others have already experienced.
- Sharing of new ideas.

4. TRAIN4EU Webinar: Transfer from academia to business and society

On November 27, 2023, Sorbonne University TRAIN4EU in collaboration with the 4EU+ local team will host a webinar on 'Transfer from academia to business and society'. It is scheduled to run from 9:30 to 13:00 and will be conducted entirely online. The planned programme is as follows:

09.30	Welcome and Introduction (30 min) Chair: Prof. Sabine Bottin-Rousseau, Sorbonne Université, Coordinator of 4EU+ EUP
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Prof. Guillaume Fiquet - Sorbonne Université - Vice-Rector International affairs - Jorge Molina- Martinez - EU Commission - Project Adviser - Research Executive Agency (REA) - Manon Prado – Policy Officer – EU Commission – DG Research and Innovation
10.00 – 11.15	Part 1. Success stories in pairs (academics and industry) (1H15) Moderators: Prof. Sabine Bottin-Rousseau, Coordinator of 4EU+ EUP and Lucas Ravaux - Deputy Director of Research and Innovation, Sorbonne University
	Presentations by: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - UW: ExplorNA Therapeutics - Prof. Jemielity - C.E.O / University of Warsaw - Laboratory of Chemical Biology and Biophysical Chemistry - SU: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • SpineGuard - T. Chandanson – R&D Director and Prof. G. Morel – ISIR Institute – Director • Basecamp vascular – DR. R. Blanc – co-founder / Head of Interventional Neuroradiology at the Hospital Fondation Adolphe de Rothschild • 4 moving biotech – Prof. F. Berenbaum – Medical Director – SU and APHP and R. Rattenbach (PHD) – CEO
	Q&A session (15min)
11.15 – 12.30	Part 2. Keynotes on transfer issues (1H15) Moderators: Prof. Sabine Bottin-Rousseau, Coordinator of 4EU+ EUP and Lucas Ravaux - Deputy Director of Research and Innovation, Sorbonne University
	Presented by: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - SSH Transfer (Maria Pontois – CNRS - Institute of Human and Social Sciences - head of management – Silver medal) - Entrepreneurship training (Hervé Marc – Sorbonne Université - DU entrepreneurship- head of training) - Relation with SME's (Clarisse Angelier – ANRT - General Delegate)
	Q&A session (10 min)
12.30 – 12.50	Round table discussion (20 min) Moderator: Prof. Sabine Bottin-Rousseau, Sorbonne Univ., Coordinator of 4EU+ EUP
12.50 – 13.00	Conclusion / End of Conference (10 min)

The webinar aims to serve as a pivotal convergence point for representatives from 4EU+ member universities, European Commission officials, and vital socio-economic partners. Its aim is to dissect and elucidate the intricate dynamics of academia's symbiotic relationship with the business sector and society.

Within the overarching framework of the TRAIN4EU project, specifically under the scope of Work Package 4: Linking citizens-academia-business (lead by Sorbonne University), this webinar is strategically designed to spotlight the efficacy of the academic-business link. Its focal point lies in extrapolating insights from the 4EU+ Alliance's collaborative experiences with socio-economic partners, thereby substantiating the interplay between academia and business.

Additionally, this event will serve as a platform for a detailed examination of academia-business exchanges through thematic lenses.

The slated agenda encompasses:

- A dedicated session spotlighting successful academia-to-business transitions within the 4EU+ member universities.
- Valuable contributions from distinguished keynote speakers, offering nuanced perspectives and profound insights into academia-business transfers, notably emphasizing Social Sciences and Humanities (SSH), entrepreneurship education, and productive collaborations with Small and Medium Enterprises (SMEs).

This meticulously curated program aims to present empirical evidence and qualitative assessments, fostering a comprehensive understanding of the symbiotic relationship between academia and the business realm. It is poised to enrich participants with actionable insights and foster discussions that illuminate the pathways for robust academia-business engagements.

Expected Outputs:

- **Identification of best practices for knowledge transfer between academia and industry:** The webinar explored a range of strategies for effectively transferring knowledge from universities to businesses, including:
 - **Establishing formal partnerships between universities and businesses:** These partnerships can facilitate collaboration on research projects, joint training programs, and technology commercialization efforts.
 - **Creating dedicated innovation hubs and incubators:** These spaces provide support for early-stage startups and entrepreneurs, enabling them to connect with university researchers and access resources to turn their ideas into viable businesses.
 - **Encouraging faculty engagement with industry:** Universities can foster a culture of entrepreneurship among faculty by providing them with training and resources to commercialize their research and engage with industry partners.
- **Development of strategies for promoting entrepreneurship and innovation within universities:** The webinar discussed the importance of fostering an entrepreneurial mindset within universities, emphasizing the need for:
 - **Incorporating entrepreneurship education into the curriculum:** Universities can integrate entrepreneurship training into existing courses or offer dedicated

entrepreneurship programs to equip students with the skills and knowledge they need to start their own businesses.

- **Providing access to mentorship and support:** Universities can connect aspiring entrepreneurs with mentors and advisors who can provide guidance and support throughout the startup process.
- **Creating a supportive ecosystem for innovation:** Universities can foster a culture of innovation by establishing makerspaces, hosting hackathons, and organizing entrepreneurship competitions.
- **Establishment of networks for collaboration between universities and socioeconomic partners:** The webinar highlighted the importance of building networks to facilitate collaboration between universities, businesses, and other socioeconomic entities. These networks can provide opportunities for:
 - **Sharing knowledge and expertise:** Universities and businesses can exchange knowledge and expertise in areas of mutual interest, leading to the development of new products, services, and processes.
 - **Joint research and development:** Universities and businesses can collaborate on research projects that address real-world challenges and contribute to technological advancements.
 - **Talent development and recruitment:** Universities can partner with businesses to provide students with internships, apprenticeships, and employment opportunities, ensuring that they graduate with the skills and experience they need to succeed in the workforce.

CONCLUSION AND PERSPECTIVES

After three years of enriching discussions, it is clear that the TRAIN4EU project has successfully bridged the gap between academia, business, and society. WP4 participants have engaged in meaningful exchanges, exploring the diverse challenges and innovative solutions that universities have developed to address the multifaceted needs of their communities.

These past three years have seen a significant exchange of knowledge between the partner universities, demonstrating their shared ideals, while acknowledging the distinctive themes shaped by internal policies, regional contexts and national landscapes. Whilst identifying areas of synergy has been a crucial outcome, the project has also encountered obstacles in launching joint initiatives, resulting from resource constraints, staffing limitations and diverging institutional priorities.

Despite these challenges, the continued discourse has facilitated recognition of prevalent patterns, recurrent obstacles, and optimum approaches for cultivating an enhanced comprehension of innovation, technology transfer, entrepreneurship, and partnerships with socioeconomic entities, encompassing SMEs, corporations, and local governmental bodies.

The achievements of the project, accomplished against the challenging backdrop presented by the COVID-19 pandemic, highlight the impressive adaptability and resilience of educational institutions in devising inventive solutions for students, researchers, faculty, and staff.

The collaborations fostered by TRAIN4EU will undoubtedly lay the groundwork for future ventures, whether undertaken individually or in partnership. The project's discussions have undoubtedly enhanced the actions and initiatives within the partner universities, laying the foundation for sustained growth and advancement.